

"HARMONY IN COMPLEXITY" • A MUSICAL DATA SONIFICATION OF ONE CENTURY OF CLIMATE DATA

Than VAN NISPEN (than.vannispn@hku.nl)¹ and Karin T. REBEL (K.T.Rebel@uu.nl)²

¹School of Music and Technology, HKU, University of the Arts Utrecht, IBBlaan 50, Utrecht, The Netherlands

²Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Environmental Sciences, Utrecht University, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

"Harmony in Complexity" transforms a century of climate data (1924-2024) into a musical experience through two distinct sonification layers: global CO₂ concentrations are mapped to sine wave frequencies, creating an evolving tonal foundation, while planetary temperature anomalies are transformed into musical notes, representing three different Northern Hemisphere zones, arranged in triads. Through interactive audience participation, the connection between the audience and the data is further enhanced. This paper describes the technical aspects of the sonification process, the theoretical framework underpinning its design and aesthetics, and discusses the potential of Art-Science collaborations to convey complex data and potentially drive transformative learning experiences.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change represents one of the most pressing environmental challenges of our time, yet the complexity and scale of climate data can make it difficult for the public to fully grasp and engage with this critical issue. "Harmony in Complexity" addresses this challenge through an Art-Science collaboration that transforms a century of climate measurements into a musical experience, embracing the Head-Hands-Heart framework for transformative sustainability education. This musical climate data sonification was developed jointly by Karin Rebel and Than van Nispen tot Pannerden as an Art-Science project for the inaugural lecture of Karin Rebel on April 2nd 2024, entitled 'Harmony in Complexity: Engaging Sustainability Science and Education for a Resilient Future'. This project emerged from the recognition that effective education and communication on environmental data require more than just cognitive understanding. Following Sipos et al.'s (2008) Head-Hands-Heart approach [1], scientific precision (Head) was combined with practical engagement (Hands) and emotional connection (Heart) through the integration of data sonification and (optional) participatory performance. This transdisciplinary approach brings together climate science and music design to create an experience that engages participants on multiple levels.

Copyright: © 2025. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

The sonification focuses on two key environmental datasets: global CO₂ concentrations and planetary temperature anomalies from 1924 to 2024. Through both artistic and scientific consideration and cooperation, the abstract numerical values are converted into an accessible musical narrative that preserves the data representation while creating an emotionally resonant experience. In the sonification process CO₂ concentrations are mapped to frequencies and temperature anomalies to musical notes, creating a dual-layer composition that reveals both the steady rise in this specific greenhouse gas and the correlating temperature changes. What further distinguishes this project is its optional integration of public participation through guided musical engagement. Rather than only presenting the sonified data with a spoken explanation as a passive listening experience, interactive elements were incorporated that transform environmental data into a shared, embodied experience. The audience becomes active participants through a performance involving body percussion (simulating natural elements like wind and rain), vocal elements, and guided musical interaction. This participatory approach creates a space where scientific data, artistic expression, and audience engagement converge.

The project addresses several themes of environmental data sonification and sustainability education:

- **Data Transparency:** The direct mapping of CO₂ levels to frequencies maintains a clear connection between the data and its sonic representation, allowing listeners to literally "hear" the rise in this greenhouse gas over time.
- **Art-Science Integration:** The project demonstrates how artistic processes can enhance scientific communication while maintaining data integrity, creating what Heinrich and Kjørnøvn [2] call the 'third space' where new insights and approaches can emerge.
- **Multi-Level Engagement:** The combination of scientific accuracy and vision, artistic interpretation, and participatory elements addresses all three aspects of the Head-Hands-Heart framework [1], creating a more complete (learning) experience.
- **Transformative Learning:** The interactive nature of the performance moves beyond traditional data presentation to create a shared experience that can drive deeper understanding and connection with environmental issues.

This paper presents the sonification implementation in Max/MSP ¹, explains the theoretical framework supporting design decisions, explores the effectiveness of participatory elements in environmental data communication and sonification, and demonstrates art-science integration for sustainability education.

2. DATASETS

Climate change is driven by anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gasses by fossil fuel burning and land use change (IPCC) [3]. CO₂ is the primary anthropogenic greenhouse gas driving climate change. Emitted CO₂ is not broken down in the atmosphere, but partly taken up by vegetation, partly absorbed by the ocean, and the rest stays in the atmosphere, increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentration [4]. The increase in atmospheric CO₂ leads to a temperature rise globally, as expressed by global temperature anomalies. In this sonification, these two key climate variables were chosen, realising that other important variables and parameters related to climate change were left out.

2.1 Global CO₂ Concentration

Two datasets have been used for one century of global CO₂ concentrations:

- the NOAA Global monitoring dataset for the reconstructed values from 1924 – 1958 [5]
- the Mauna Loa dataset, which starts its measurements in the year 1958 and has monthly averages of the CO₂ concentration in Mauna Loa [6, 7].

The Mauna Loa dataset is the longest record of direct measurements of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Mauna Loa in Hawaii is located in a remote location in the Pacific Ocean at high altitude and with large distance from major pollution sources.

To extend the dataset to 100 years, the NOAA constructed values dataset was used for the period before Mauna Loa.

2.2 Temperature anomalies

Rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations drive global temperature increases, though this warming is not uniform across the globe. Higher latitude temperatures are increasing faster than lower latitudes. This is represented in the temperature anomaly dataset [8], where the data are divided into the arctic (latitude 90N-64N), temperate (latitude 64N-24N) and the tropical (latitude 24N-EQ) region.

The temperature anomalies are the differences, positive or negative, of the temperature relative to a baseline, or reference period, which is in this case the average temperatures between the years 1951-1980. These temperature anomalies allow for comparison between different regions regardless of their absolute temperatures.

¹ Max/MSP (Version 8.5.1) is a visual programming environment developed by Cycling '74. <https://cycling74.com>

3. DATA SONIFICATION

The Sonification Handbook [9] opens with: “*Imagine listening to changes in global temperature over the last thousand years.*” Apart from the timeframe, this quote captures both an essence of Data sonification and a scope for this project. Sonification is considered the “... *transformation of data relations into perceived relations in an acoustic signal for the purposes of facilitating communication or interpretation.*”

At HKU, our approach to data sonification, or musification (musical sonification) considers two major aspects:

- (A) The clarity, comprehensibility, and/or integrity of the data representation, ensuring the sonification accurately reflects the original data.
- (B) The aesthetics of the sonification and the intended emotional and cognitive response it evokes (representing the essence and/or purpose of the data)

This can depend on for instance the goal of the sonification.

One can easily imagine that directly transforming dataset values into frequencies of a sine wave can give a clear understanding of the values of the dataset (A), but doesn't necessarily become emotionally resonant, or even an aesthetically compelling experience (B). When translating, representing, or ‘mapping’ the data to the sonification there is always an artistic decision being made, balancing between A and B, often involving math and/or more abstract interpretation of data. Sometimes on the extreme spectrum of B the sensation of the data, the story behind the data (or “how does the data make you feel?”) is more important than the actual data, but making the relation to the data very abstract.

In the context of this project the aim was to explore the possibilities to stay both close to A, while aesthetically conveying an artistic message, B, that also makes the listener feel (heart).

3.1 CO₂ sonification

As mentioned in section 2 two datasets have been used for the sonification of CO₂ data, the NOAA Global monitoring dataset for the reconstructed values from 1924 – 1958 and the Mauna Loa dataset, which starts in 1958. The atmospheric CO₂ concentration, measured in parts per million (ppm), was sonified by mapping those values to the frequency (in Hertz, Hz) of a sine wave. The sonification starts in 1924, with a CO₂ concentration of 304.7 ppm [5] corresponding to a frequency of 304.7 Hz, and performed as a short sine wave ‘beep’ (of around 300 ms, see section 3.1.2). This is called ‘layer 1’.

As a frequency of 311 Hz corresponds to a D# (D sharp), or an E♭ (E flat) note, this 304.7 Hz tone would still be an E♭ note, but tuned slightly too low. In the context of “Harmony in Complexity” the E♭ context is preferred over sharps for enharmonic reasons and the number of accidentals for notation.

From the start of 1958, the second dataset [6, 7] is used and monthly CO₂ concentration as measured on Mauna

Figure 1. Rising CO₂ concentration 1958 – 2024 → normalised values, which are used for volume automation.

Figure 2. screenshot from the Max/MSP visualisation of the CO₂ concentration (top) and normalised values (bottom).

Loa is sonified as 'layer 2'. The monthly CO₂ in ppm values are sonified to the frequency of a sine wave in Hz and the amplitude (or envelope) is now automated to the normalised CO₂ concentration, as explained in section 3.1.1

From 1958 onwards 'layer 1' is now statically playing the year-pulse at 311 Hz and serves as a reference value for the rising CO₂ concentration.

3.1.1 Sonification of the Annual Normalised CO₂ concentration

Each year's CO₂ values are normalized using the previous year's minimum and maximum values (plus a +0.075% headroom²) as scaling boundaries, creating a 0-1 range that drives the amplitude envelope of the sine wave, sounding at the frequency of the CO₂ concentration (see Figure 1 and 2).

The values from the Mauna Loa dataset mapped to the frequency of a sinewave, combined with the normalised values as the amplitude envelope sonify the monthly CO₂ concentration in a unique way as these values can be considered to represent the "breathing of the Earth" as each year CO₂ concentration is taken up from the atmosphere in the summer and released in the winter [7].

The data ends with the measurements of January 2024, corresponding with a CO₂ value of 422.8 ppm. 422.8 Hz corresponds to an A \flat (A flat) note, slightly higher (detuned) than a pure A \flat tone. This change, or interval, from 1924 - 2024 is called a perfect fourth³.

² the actual rise in CO₂ per year is between 0.07 and 1% (<https://www.co2.earth/daily-co2>). This value could have been used from data as well, but is now a coincidence as it is based on the aesthetics of the amplitude envelope.

³ The data are currently heading to 440 Hz, an A natural, or a so-called tritone and 'Diabolis in musica' in the context of the E \flat origin (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tritone>)

3.1.2 Timing

In the first period (1924-1958) one year of CO₂ data is sonified every 2 seconds.

The length of the 'beep' in this pre-1958 period is around 300 ms and this length is based on the CO₂ concentration. The CO₂-value is divided by two and the first half is used for the ramp up of the amplitude envelope and the second half for the ramp down. This envelope is thus a very subtle sonification of the CO₂ concentration. For the second period (1958-2024) the data for one year is sonified in 3 seconds, with 12 steps for the 12 months of the year (or 250 ms per month). The year 1958 is an exception as the earliest value available is March 1958. This 10-month period for 1958 corresponds to 2.5 seconds and conveniently forms a transition in timing intervals between the first (2 seconds per year) and second period (3 seconds per year). This timing also drives the notes, as described in 3.2.3.

This shift from 2 to 3 seconds per year was chosen for aesthetic reasons (tempo and pace) and primarily because of the lower information density and very slow rise of CO₂ in the years preceding 1958.

3.2 Musification of planetary temperature anomalies

3.2.1 Baseline

The planetary anomalies represent temperature differences to a baseline. To musically sonify (musify) the values to MIDI notes, a baseline for the musical note differences is desired. This value should be considered as a reference point similar to a baseline, a zero, or neutral white colour in the visual equivalent of this data musification, also known as the "climate (warming) stripes" [10]. For "Harmony in Complexity" a baseline is chosen on as center C, MIDI note value 60. The 60 value could be arbitrarily chosen, but has several backgrounds. First the value of +57 has been explored, based on 57 Fahrenheit (F) being the average world temperature for 1900-2000 (13.9°C).

The 60 value however also has a clear connotation with being the centre of the keyboard and piano staff, making it visually easy to understand whether the temperature is below, or above the centre value. To be able to shift the baseline and set the key of the musification also makes it easier to transpose to other keys. Therefore this baseline value is a variable in the application.

3.2.2 Musification of temperature anomalies

Temperature anomalies are mapped linearly to semitones, with $\pm 1.2^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to ± 12 semitones (octave), then rounded to the nearest scale tone.

Temperature-to-MIDI mapping can use either continuous float values (allowing microtones) or integer values (semitones only). For aesthetic reasons and to avoid artificially dramatizing the data, integer values were chosen using floor rounding, which consistently rounds to lower rather than higher note values.

Without any further processing of the 12 semitones the music could be considered as somewhat twelve tones music, which is often considered and experienced as atonal music [11]. (This can be experienced in the "Harmony in

Figure 3. Note values from temperature anomalies data to semitones, in an Eb major (or Cm) scale, and climate stripes colour approach

Complexity" application, which is available on request.) The 12 semitones can also be scaled to nearest values within one, or more, musical scales, like the major, or Ionian scale (see Figure 3) . The note values resulting from the data are rounded to the nearest musical note that fits in the Ionian scale in Eb. For this context the musical notes are rounded to the lowest nearest value. Because of this fact and the previously mentioned integer context, the musification should therefore be considered as a slightly "less alarming" version of the actual data, regarding the perceived height of the notes as these are rounded to lower values.

For notes extending the values of the scale (smaller than 0, larger than 11), modulo 12 is first applied, as in Equation (1), calculated to the scale and then adjusted for the octave(s).

$$a \% 12 \text{ (or } a \text{ mod } 12) \tag{1}$$

Example: a temperature anomaly of 1.6 °C, resulting in a musical note with value 16 would become $16 \% 12 = 4$. This value 4 would correspond to 3 in the Ionian scale of Eb. The octave is corresponding to $\text{floor}(16/12) = 1$ octave. This octave is added as $1 * 12 = 12$ semitones to the outcome of 3, or note value $12 + 3 = 15$ to be added to the baseline. This temperature anomaly of 1.6 °C eventually sounds as MIDI note value $60 + 15 = 75$

For the "listening version", in the temperature anomalies data musification the musical mode changes in 2013 from a major to a harmonic minor scale, as 2013 marks the year the 400 ppm CO2 value is passed for the first time. In the second version, or the version for engagement, the mode doesn't change and stays in the major scale.

3.2.3 Three zones, three notes

For this context the Northern Hemisphere (NH) is divided in three zones, the equator (24N-EQU), temperate region (64N-24N) and pole (64N-90N). For the temperate region an average of the two NASA dataset values, 64N-44N and 44N-24N, is calculated in Max/MSP and used for further processing.

The temperature anomalies for the three zones are first played as a triad and then separately as notes representing the equator, followed by the temperate region and finally by the north pole. The timing of each of these four beats is every 3 months of data, or 750 ms. (see subsection 3.1.2) These notes are also displayed (see Figure 4).

These musical notes can be interpreted by any instrument. For the context of "Harmony in Complexity" this musification of planetary temperature anomalies starts halfway the century of data, 50 years after the start in 1924, in the

Figure 4. Screenshot of music notes in Max/MSP representing the temperature anomalies for the Northern Hemisphere

year 1974 and is performed by piano. This musification is played as 'layer 3' on top of 'layer 1' and 'layer 2' as explained in section 3.1.

The relatively silent beginning, before the piano starts, gives room for a narrator to explain the data, the translation of data to sound and to introduce the musification. It also gives room for some (dramatic) silence in between the year beeps, which also engages the audience in attentive listening.

3.3 Live Performance Implementation

In the inaugural lecture by Professor Karin Rebel, the theory around climate change was explained (Head, cognitive) and transdisciplinary education including project- and challenge-based learning was explained (Head-Hands). Related to climate change research and education, figures from the IPCC and the Global Carbon project were shared, as was a personal intergenerational timeline related to CO2 concentration in the atmosphere. Concluding this lecture, the 'listening version' of "Harmony in Complexity" was presented with scripted spoken word narration explaining the data sonification. [A live recording of this sonification with narrative can be viewed on : <https://youtu.be/vLCXT7iYpso>]

3.3.1 Engagement

For "Harmony in Complexity", an additional experience was designed to transform passive listening into active participation: sonic engagement with the audience that served as a metaphorical invitation to collective climate action. To engage and to apply the Head-Hands-Heart framework, a follow-up approach was developed, inspired by Jacob Collier's "audience choir" [12] for a sonification version with audience engagement. Elements that were inspired by Jacob Collier were the conducting of musical notes via the height of the hands, as well as making a big gesture (hands apart) for louder singing and a small gesture (hands closely together) for softer singing and the end. The diverse audience of over 200 people -including friends, colleagues, and family members from various backgrounds, disciplines, ages, nationalities, and genders- were invited to contribute actively to the performance. The audience was divided into 3 groups and the previous sonification was now started from the year 2000. The groups started with body percussion, by rubbing hands to mimic wind (group 1), finger clicking to mimic rain (group 2), and a simple breathing in and out for group 3. This exercise was to include the hands, create a collective sound layer, relating

to the data narrative as well as to loosen up the audience for participation. Group 3 then began to follow the starting tone representing the CO₂ concentration (E ♭) with repeated short 'Ooh' (/u:/) sounds, establishing a rhythmic pulse.

Next the groups were invited to sing short and continuous E ♭ notes, followed by E ♭ -A ♭ 's, with the A ♭ being a fourth above the E ♭ and also sung continuously. The heights of the notes were indicated by conducting the audience groups with the height of the hand representing the height of the note. Finally the E ♭ -A ♭ was followed by a C natural, leading to an A ♭ -major triad in second inversion (E ♭ -A ♭ -C). This triad was collectively sung louder, softer and eventually ended via hand gestures.

This A ♭ major triad was intentionally chosen for several reasons:

1. First, the CO₂ sonification evolved from an E ♭ to an A ♭ in one century time.
2. Secondly this major chord creates a "feel-good" ending that sounds harmonious. However, within the musical context, it doesn't feel like a final ending, but rather a prelude to further action, as it functions as the IV chord (A ♭) in the key of E ♭. Additionally, the A ♭ note as well as the chord can be interpreted as representing the new (temporary) reality—the altered context resulting from a century of CO₂ increase.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Society is facing large sustainability challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity loss and feeding the world's population. It is acknowledged that these challenges can only be solved using an inter- and transdisciplinary approach. However, systems change is needed to progress towards a sustainable and resilient future. To reach this, effective learning objectives need to be included, next to cognitive learning objectives and practical skill development. While no formal qualitative or quantitative research was conducted for 'Harmony in Complexity', some of the anecdotal observations are considered worth sharing, but deserve further (practice based) research.

4.1 Sonification

In very direct mapping between data to music, or sound, the results are not necessarily aesthetically compelling [9, 13]. In the direct mapping from CO₂ concentration in ppm to frequency in Hz, the resulting pitches and envelopes were actually surprisingly musical and very well usable in both explaining and experiencing the rising CO₂ concentration. The reason why this sonification of CO₂ concentration was explored in the beginning was to demonstrate the kind of sonification that would actually be undesirable for this project. The resulting pitches and envelopes however were surprisingly musical and proved the first assumption of poor aesthetics of raw data sonification wrong, especially in combination with the more musical mapping of

temperature anomalies to musical notes via simple musical scales. As can be seen and heard, the data used in this project by its sheer values and sonification thereof turned out to be aesthetically very usable.

As was mentioned in subsection 3.2.3 it was decided during the composition process that the musification of the temperature anomalies (piano music) should begin after 50 years of CO₂ data sonification, in 1974. This musical buildup worked really well for this context.

The combination of staying close to the original data while realising aesthetically interesting music and certainly making the audience feel something is considered successful in this project.

In rounding values to musical scales one can question the balance between transparently representing the data on the one hand, and creating an emotional response of the listener on the other hand. The implications of designing this affective experience, surrounding climate science and data is an important point for further discussion. An ethics discussion on musical data sonification and the emotional impact of different scales, would be very valuable, but are outside the scope of this paper.

4.2 Live Performance Implementation

Sonifications of climate data are not new [9, 14]. However, similar to music composition where musical themes can sometimes be the same, but still result in completely different, unique music, every take on the same data can lead to unique sonifications and experiences.

Besides the sonification of both CO₂ and temperature anomalies, in "Harmony in Complexity" an additional experience was explored to transform passive listening into active participation: a sounding engagement with the audience. As mentioned in subsection 3.2.2 the musification version used for engagement stayed in the major (Ionian) scale, which added to a positive affect. The subtle difference in listening and participation versions appeared successful.

The more complex you make the musical engagement, the more difficult it might become and the riskier it may be for realising an effective and intended emotional response. To limit these risks and a higher chance for a successful result a few audience members were in the know.

4.3 Head-Hands-Heart integration

The transition from Head (data and graphs) to Hands and Hearts, via sonification, musification and engagement was considered successful. The musical sonification connected with the affective feelings of the audience, and the collective feeling of a positive resolution was reached by engagement with a highly diverse audience with intergenerational and intercultural differences, reflecting that solutions can be found in the interdisciplinary and inclusive space of engagement.

Afterwards, people from the audience commented on the different emotions that they experienced during the event, which were feelings of loss and sadness as well as beauty and hope. People from the audience commented on this experience even half a year after the event. Members of

the audience mentioned afterwards that they were hearing and experiencing birdsong outside of the venue, during the moments of silence in the early beginning of the sonification and felt very present.

The authors consider this a successful and promising example of how artistic processes can enhance scientific communication, while maintaining data and information integrity.

4.4 Future work

In “Harmony in Complexity” one century of CO₂ concentrations and temperature anomalies for the Northern Hemisphere have been sonified. The data sonification method can also easily be used for the Southern Hemisphere, other data and datasets. This has been experimented with and adds promising musical layers, or variations, such as arpeggios with local temperatures, a counterpoint with other (greenhouse) gasses, precipitation, etc. Further ambitions include live performances of the sonification of “Harmony in Complexity”.

The Harmony in Complexity Max/MSP application, resulting sonification, (sheet) music, as well as guidelines for the audience engagement are freely available. If you would like to use it for your specific context, you’re invited to contact the authors.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank UU and HKU colleagues. Special thanks, credits and mention should be made to the HKU students from the talented year 3 Sonic Interaction Design group that were involved in the early brainstorming phase of the project, suggesting elements such as audience participation and active engagement with the data.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Sipos, B. Battisti, and K. Grimm, “Achieving transformative sustainability learning: Engaging head, hands and heart.” *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education.*, vol. 9, no. 10.1108/14676370810842193, pp. 68–86, 2008.
- [2] F. Heinrich and L. Kørnøv, “Art and higher education for environmental sustainability: a matter of emergence?” *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 483–503, 2021.
- [3] H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, M. Tignor, E. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösche, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama, D. Belling, W. Dieck, S. Götze, T. Kersher, P. Mangele, B. Maus, A. Mühle, and N. Weyer, *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, 08 2022.
- [4] P. Friedlingstein, M. O’Sullivan, M. W. Jones, R. M. Andrew, D. C. E. Bakker, J. Hauck, P. Landschützer, C. Le Quéré, I. T. Luijckx, G. P. Peters, W. Peters, J. Pongratz, C. Schwingshackl, S. Sitch, J. G. Canadell, P. Ciais, and Jackson, “Global carbon budget 2023,” *Earth System Science Data*, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 5301–5369, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/15/5301/2023/>
- [5] H. Ritchie, P. Rosado, and V. Samborska, ““data page: Annual concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide”, part of the following publication: Hannah ritchie, pablo rosado, and veronika samborska (2024) - “climate change”. data adapted from noaa global monitoring laboratory, united states environmental protection agency.” [Online]. Available: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/co2-long-term-concentration>
- [6] C. Keeling, R. Bacastow, A. Bainbridge, C. Jr, P. Guenther, L. Waterman, and J. Chin, “Atmospheric carbon dioxide variations at mauna loa observatory, hawaii,” *Tellus*, vol. 28, pp. 538 – 551, 03 2010.
- [7] C. Keeling, S. Piper, R. Bacastow, M. Wahlen, T. Whorf, T. Heimann, and H. A. Meijer, *A History of Atmospheric CO2 and Its Effects on Plants, Animals, and Ecosystems.*, ser. Ecological Studies. Springer, 01 2005, vol. 177, ch. Atmospheric CO2 and 13CO2 exchange with the terrestrial biosphere and oceans from 1978 to 2000: observations and carbon cycle implications, in *A History of Atmospheric CO2 and Its Effects on Plants, Animals, and Ecosystems*, pp. 88–113.
- [8] <https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/>, “Gistemp team, 2024: Giss surface temperature analysis (gistemp), version 4. nasa goddard institute for space studies. zonal annual means, 1880-present zonal annual means, 1880-present, updated through most recent complete year.”
- [9] H. Thomas, H. Andy, and N. J. G. (Eds.), *The Sonification Handbook*. Logos Verlag, 2011.
- [10] E. Hawkins, *Climate Lab Book*, 12 2018, vol. visualisation update / Warming stripes for 1850–2018 using the WMO annual global temperature dataset.
- [11] W. de Ruiter, *Compositietechnieken in de twintigste eeuw*. De Toorts, Haarlem, 1993.
- [12] “Jacob collier - the audience choir (live at o2 academy brixton, london),” August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://youtu.be/3KsF309XpJo>
- [13] L. Lintmeijer, P. Beek, M. Hofmijster, and S. Huiberts, “Row your beat: the development of an innovative auditory feedback platform for rowing performance,” 07 2018.
- [14] S. S. George, D. Crawford, T. Reubold, and E. Giorgi, “Making climate data sing: Using music-like sonifications to convey a key climate record,” *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, vol. 98, pp. 23–27, January 2017.